

Detailed study of fluorescent properties of cyclodextrin complexes for sensitive automated determination of diclofenac metabolism using the sequential injection system

Ivana Pekařová, Michaela Váňová, Petr Chocholouš

Department of Analytical Chemistry, Faculty of Pharmacy in Hradec Králové, Charles University, Akademika Heyrovského 1203, 500 03, Hradec Králové, Czech Republic

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Automation
Cyclodextrin complex
Diclofenac
Fluorescence
Sequential injection analysis

ABSTRACT

A simple and rapid method for determining diclofenac in a sequential injection system was developed for the selective and sensitive on-line determination of the analyte in sample from a metabolic study. The fluorescence properties of complexes of 13 types of cyclodextrins and their derivatives, including salts, were studied off-line, while two of the complexes were then used in the flow conditions. Optimisation was carried out with (2-hydroxypropyl)- γ -cyclodextrin, which is fluorescent and the intensity of its complex with diclofenac was found to be lower. In the flow system, we tested different types of mixing of zones and stop-flow periods. Simple mixing using flow reversal and a 1-min stop-flow in the holding coil were sufficient to rapidly determine diclofenac, even at low concentrations with a limit of quantitation of 1×10^{-6} mol/L. The relationship between fluorescence intensity and diclofenac concentration showed a different pattern in the two intervals: decreasing in the range of $1-5 \times 10^{-7}$ mol/l and linearly increasing in the range of $1-5 \times 10^{-6}$ mol/l, which was used for analysis. Real samples from a metabolic activity study based on the activation of xenobiotics recognition receptors were analysed, and the results were compared with off-line liquid chromatography/mass spectrometry measurements. The differences corresponded to the complexity of the matrix and were not significant. The trend of diclofenac metabolism was obvious. The developed method is prepared for the fully automated, real-time monitoring of the metabolic study with more frequent sampling than just once daily and the prediction of sample collection for the mass spectrometric determination of diclofenac metabolites.

1. Introduction

The determination of low concentrations of analytes in metabolic studies requires high sensitivity and selectivity to distinguish analytes from other compounds present at higher levels in complex samples. Although mass spectrometry (MS) coupled with liquid chromatography (LC) separation can achieve high sensitivity and selectivity, other detection techniques such as fluorometry and chemiluminescence, are available as sample preparation techniques involving preconcentration of analytes. Sensitive detection and preconcentration can easily be coupled with an automated, low-pressure system based on sequential injection analysis (SIA). Here, we report its use for rapidly determining compounds in samples derived from metabolic studies.

Developed in 1990 [1], the SIA system differs from a typical flow

injection analysis (FIA) due to its discontinuous carrier stream flow and ability to handle only lower tens microliter volumes of samples and reagents aspirated via a selection valve. This concept, known for many years [2–4], can be improved with flow programming [5,6], where the kinetics of different analytical steps are considered and transferred into the flow system. SIA and other low-pressure techniques have been extensively used to automate chemical reactions. The advantages of such automation have been demonstrated to be: (i) rapid determinations with high repeatability, (ii) low risk of error in the automated system following the control program, (iii) easy coupling with on-line sampling from long-term processes such as metabolic or toxicological studies, and last but not least, (iv) easy testing of reaction kinetics, stability, and behaviour of the reaction products generated. Automation in low-pressure flow systems is currently applied in two areas: (i)

This article is part of a special issue entitled: ICFA 2024 published in Talanta.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: chocholous@faf.cuni.cz (P. Chocholouš), svecfr@faf.cuni.cz (F. Švec), sklenarova@faf.cuni.cz (H. Sklenářová).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2025.128847>

Received 28 March 2025; Received in revised form 28 August 2025; Accepted 10 September 2025

Available online 12 September 2025

0039-9140/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

automation of sample preparation and (ii) monitoring of long-term processes during sampling at preset time intervals coupled with on-line determination of the analyte of interest. For sample preparation, on-line coupling to LC or other separation systems is advantageous. Monitoring applications range from dissolution testing of solid dosage forms to interactions of biologically active substances with membrane transporters, and to toxicity visualisation by changes in cell membranes permeability [7,8].

This study focuses on determining diclofenac (DCF). This drug was also used in an independent project involving the metabolism of DCF to quantify the expression and metabolic activity of genes that regulate receptors for the recognition of xenobiotics and the coordination of their detoxification [9]. In that study, samples were produced in a complex matrix including test substances in a cultivation medium taken from a well plate containing primary human hepatocyte spheroids, and the samples were analysed by LC-MS/MS. Our research addressed some of the disadvantages of their approach, which used sensitive fluorescence (FL) to determine DCF.

Unfortunately, the FL of DCF alone is very low. However, it is known that the fluorescence of compounds can be enhanced by forming complexes with cyclodextrins (CD). These complexes with various compounds have already been described in the literature [10–15]. Table 1 shows the DCF complexes with different types of CDs such as α -CD, β -CD, γ -CD, and hydroxypropyl- β -CD. These complexes have been studied previously under batch conditions [16–20]. The CD concentrations were in the range of 4×10^{-3} – 1×10^{-2} mol/L. The optimal excitation (EX) and emission (EM) wavelengths were affected by pH or by the combination with another fluorophore, such as pyrene [19]. Using a simple pH adjustment, an EX of 289 and an EM of 362 nm were found [16–18]. Alternatively, UV irradiation has been used, and completely different EX/EM values have been reported [20].

Derivatization has also been used [21] with calibration ranges and limits of quantitation (LOQ) even lower than those found for the DCF:CD complexes shown in Table 1. However, the derivatization reaction alone took 30 min, including heating and cooling steps that significantly increased the analysis time. This was another reason for our choice of on-line DCF:CD complex formation and fluorescence determination in the SIA system. The CD complexation concept also seemed applicable with the perspective for faster optimisation and potential transfer to determination under flow conditions. In this study, we tested the fluorescence of DCF complexes with different CDs, their stability, and their

potential for transfer to the SIA system. We found the optimised conditions and adjusted them to accommodate small sample volumes, to improve sensitivity, and to test the stop-flow approach in the flow cell. Finally, we used SIA to determine of DCF in real-life samples and compared our results with those previously obtained by LC-MS/MS determination [9].

The main objective of the presented work was to develop an easy and rapid method for determining DCF in a complex matrix of samples from a metabolic study involving primary human hepatocytes, which contain cultivation medium, the tested substances, the solvent, and other components. The primary human hepatocyte model is a modern alternative for *in vitro* testing of the activation of receptors that are responsible for recognizing xenobiotics and coordinating their detoxification. Three-dimensional (3D) spheroids prepared from the suspension of primary hepatocytes were treated and cultivated following previously published procedures [9]. In our study, we measured the same samples in the SIA system with fluorescence detection while inducing cytochrome CYP3A4 activity with rifampicin. DCF was used as a model substance, as its metabolism is well-understood and can be monitored to visualize the cytochrome activity. Continuing research in this field supports trends in the testing of new biologically active compounds and drugs.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Reagents and sample preparation

Unless otherwise stated, standards of all other chemicals were obtained from Sigma Aldrich (Prague, Czech Republic). Diclofenac sodium salt was obtained from the accredited laboratory (the Department of Analytical Chemistry, Faculty of Pharmacy, Charles University, DS/0405/120B). Carboxymethyl- α -CD ($\geq 97\%$), (2-hydroxypropyl)- γ -CD, carboxymethyl- β -CD sodium salt, succinyl- β -CD, β -CD hydrate, (2-hydroxypropyl)- α -CD, and the sodium salts of sulphated α -CD, α -CD-hydrate, γ -CD ($\geq 99\%$), and β -CD were obtained from Fluka Chemika, Switzerland. Dimethyl- β -CD, hydroxypropyl- β -CD, and carboxymethyl- γ -CD were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany). The properties of all tested CDs with respect to the number of glucose units, molecular weight, cavity inner diameter, cavity depth, solubility in water, and pKa are listed in Supplementary material (Table S1). Ultrapure water for solutions, dilution, washing the SIA system, and as a carrier stream in the SIA system was produced using the Milli-Q Direct

Table 1

List of previously reported fluorometric studies related to DCF using CD complexes and derivatization.

Reaction/CD	Concentration of CD (mol/L)	Ratio DCF:CD	Diluent	Conditioning	Temperature (°C)	EX/EM wavelength (nm)	Calibration range LOQ (mg/L)	Ref.
Complexation/ α -CD, β -CD	6×10^{-3}	1:1	water	pH adjustment (NaOH and HClO ₄)	20	289/362	0–5 0.07	[16, 17]
Complexation/ β -CD	6×10^{-3}	1:1	water	pH adjustment (NaOH and HClO ₄)	20	289/362	0.03–5 0.03	[18]
Complexation/ α / β / γ -CD, hydroxypropyl- β -CD	0.4×10^{-3}	1:1	water	pyrene (1×10^{-3} mol/L) as fluorophore	25	340/350–450	–	[19]
UV light irradiation in flow conditions	–	–	–	UV at 254 nm for 15 s	20	279/420	1×10^{-6} – 1×10^{-4} mol/L 2×10^{-6} mol/L	[20]
Derivatization	–	–	methanol	borate buffer (0.1 mol/L); derivatization with NBD-F ^{a)}	Heating to 70 °C (30 min) + cooling down	464/521	0.025–0.50 0.165 μ g/L	[21]
Complexation	1×10^{-4}	1:1	cultivation medium	1 min stop-flow	20	290/364.5	1×10^{-7} – 5×10^{-7} mol/L 1×10^{-6} – 5×10^{-6} mol/L 0.032	This work

*,

^{a)} NBD-F = 7-fluoro-4-nitrobenzo-2-oxa-1,3-diazole.

Water Purification System (Merck, Czech Republic). Ethanol denatured with methanol (96 %, Lihovar Kolín, Czech Republic) was used to clean the SIA system after measuring real-life samples including the cultivation medium. Opti-MEM reduced serum and Williams Phenol Red medium without fetal bovine serum (Life Technologies Corporation, USA) were used as in the experiments described elsewhere [9].

A stock solution of DCF was prepared at a concentration of 1×10^{-2} mol/L, which was then diluted with water to reach the desired concentrations. The DCF solutions were stored in the refrigerator at 5 °C and brought to the laboratory temperature (22 °C) at least 30 min prior to measurement. All DCF and CD solutions were then kept at the laboratory temperature. Aqueous CD stock solutions were also prepared at a concentration of 1×10^{-2} mol/L and diluted to the desired testing concentration. Complexes that were tested off-line were prepared from DCF:CD solutions with different concentrations at v/v ratios of 1:1, 1:2, and 2:1. These complexes were measured on the same day and on the next day after the mixing to observe the kinetics of complex formation.

Calibration was performed using stop-flow periods of 1 and 10 min with DCF in the concentration range of 1×10^{-6} – 1×10^{-5} mol/L, and (2-hydroxypropyl)- γ -CD at concentrations of 1×10^{-2} , 1×10^{-3} , and 1×10^{-4} mol/L. Aqueous DCF solutions were tested first, followed by DCF diluted with cultivation medium to detect possible interferences from other compounds. All standard solutions were measured in triplicate and the average was used for the calibration. Repeatability was expressed as RSD.

The real-life samples consisted of cultivation medium used to cultivate primary human hepatocyte spheroids, as well as the substances being tested. In our case, these substances were 1×10^{-5} mol/L DCF as a substrate, 1×10^{-5} mol/L rifampicin to induce metabolic activity, and DMSO as a solvent for the tested substances. As a control, samples without rifampicin were analysed with only the same volume of DMSO.

2.2. Fluorometer and sequential injection system

The RF 6000 spectrofluorometer (Shimadzu Europe GmbH, Germany) was controlled by LabSolutions RF software, and measurements were performed in Spectrum and Time course modes. The open-top batch quartz cuvette (Agilent Technologies, Germany) with an optical path of 10×10 mm and a volume of 3.0 mL was used for off-line measurements. A flow-through Suprasil® quartz cuvette with a spectral range of 200–2500 nm, optical path 3×3 mm, and a volume of 100

μ L (Hellma Analytics, Germany) was used for flow measurements.

For measurements under flow conditions, a MicroSIA system (FIALab Instruments, USA, Fig. 1) with a 6-port selection valve and a 2.5 mL piston pump, which was controlled by FIALab software for Windows 5.0, was connected to the flow-through cuvette in the spectrofluorometer via polytetrafluoroethylene tubing (i.d. 0.75 mm). The piston pump was equipped with a two-way valve to aspirate the carrier in the IN position and the other liquids through the selection valve in the OUT position. A holding coil of the same tubing was inserted between the piston pump and the selection valve to prevent the piston from coming into contact with the solutions. The tube connecting to the spectrofluorometer was covered with aluminum foil to eliminate the noise of external light from entering the flow cuvette. Samples for off-line SIA measurements were introduced through the selection valve port via short PEAK tubing, while samples for on-line monitoring were introduced via tubing from the respective sampling coil connected to the apical or basolateral parts of the 3D-printed module and again to the selection valve port [7,8]. The module was designed to sample from both sides of the cell monolayer cultivated on a commercial insert. It was placed inside an incubator to maintain life conditions for the tested cells during long-term monitoring. Coupling of the module with the SIA system enables on-line determination of different markers and provide real-time information.

2.3. Optimisation of formation of DCF:CD complexes

Preliminary testing of the formation of the DCF:CD complex consisted of off-line fluorescence measurements of DCF, CD, and their mixtures as specified in section 2.1 by manually loading of solutions into the batch quartz cuvette. EX and EM wavelengths were monitored in the Spectrum mode.

Under flow conditions, two of the tested CDs were selected and the same ratios and concentrations were used in the SIA system while the monitoring fluorescence intensity. We also tested the aspirated volumes, concentrations, ratios, and means of mixing in the SIA system, as well as the pre-mixed zones were also aspirated in the SIA, to gain a detailed understanding of complex formation.

Then, the calibration range with limits of detection and quantitation were tested at different DCF:CD concentration ratios keeping the volume of both solutions at 30 μ L and the concentration of the CD solution higher than that of the DCF standards. In this step, different widths of excitation and emission bands were used to increase the sensitivity,

Fig. 1. Scheme of the SIA system for fluorometric diclofenac determination.

though this decreases selectivity by 3 and 10 nm, respectively, at the same time.

Stop-flow measurements can be applied in the flow systems for slow reactions automation. In non-equilibrium conditions when detection signal is not high enough the reacting zone can be parked in the detection cell and the signal is monitored while the reaction is continuing. Then the increasing part of the monitored signal can be evaluated by different slopes corresponding to different analyte concentrations. To further increase sensitivity, stop-flow of the mixed zone in the flow-through cuvette and evaluation based on the slope of the increasing signal were also tested.

2.4. SIA measurements of FL properties of DCF:CD complexes

Flow measurements were carried out using the Time course mode of the spectrofluorometer. Continuous signal scanning was used to evaluate the FL intensity in terms of peak height. An accumulation time of 1 s was set as the optimum to obtain a sufficient number of experimental points per peak. This parameter was closely related to the flow rate through the detector flow cell, which was optimised to 30 $\mu\text{L/s}$. Mixing was tested at flow rates of 30, 40, and 50 $\mu\text{L/s}$. Based on our preliminary results from off-line measurements, two CDs were selected for SIA, the previously reported α -CD hydrate [16] and carboxymethyl- α -CD. The DCF:CD ratios of 1:1 and 1:2 were tested under flow conditions. The aspirated volumes of both zones were 30/30 μL for the 1:1 ratio and 30/60 μL for the 1:2 ratio. To compare the FL signal of the DCF:CD complex with that of CD alone, blank measurements were performed with an aspirated zone of water instead of DCF to maintain the same flow and mixing conditions.

2.5. Selection of parameters and data evaluation

Off-line tests were used to select the respective CD types, which revealed the difference between the EM spectrum of the CD and the DCF:CD mixture. The EX/EM values were also considered, and the stability of the complexes was tested for solutions and mixtures prepared on the same day and one day later (after 24 h), accounting for the effect of temperature by storing solutions in a refrigerator and under laboratory conditions. The CD types, ratios, and concentrations were then selected for on-line testing.

The data from the on-line measurements were evaluated in Time course mode, with manual correction of the measured value to the baseline, and by averaging the FL intensity of three repeated aspirations in one run. We calculate the standard deviation and relative standard deviation, and the relative standard deviation (RSD) value did not exceed 2.5 %. This corresponds to the usual repeatability of rapid flow measurements in the SIA system. A coefficient of determination of ≥ 0.99 was required for linear or polynomial calibration curves.

The kinetic profiles of the stop-flow measurement in the flow-through cuvette were evaluated using 10 data points in the rising part of the fluorescence signal while the carrier flow was stopped. The rising curves were evaluated for their slopes, which could potentially be related to the DCF concentration.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. EX/EM spectra of DCF:CD complexes

These measurements were carried out in order to select the most suitable CD for forming a DCF:CD complex to determine DCF. To maintain the same concentration when measuring the spectra, the CD solution was diluted with water to the same extent as in the DCF:CD mixtures. Measurements of the EX/EM spectra of α -CD-hydrate showed the maxima at 290 and 380 nm, respectively. These values correspond to the reported values of 289 and 362 nm, respectively [16]. The 290 nm EX was used to monitor EM spectra in the 300–600 nm range. The

EX/EM spectral bands were broadened from 3 to 20 nm, and the sensitivity was set high to observe even slight difference in FL characteristics and differences between the tested CDs.

The EX/EM wavelengths of the different DCF:CD complexes made it possible to classify all the tested CDs into four groups with different characteristics and allowed comparison of the CDs spectra themselves and their DCF:CD complexes. The first group consisted of α -CD-hydrate, β -CD-hydrate, γ -CD, (2-hydroxypropyl)- γ -CD, dimethyl- β -CD, and succinyl- β -CD. These CDs provided EM spectra only for aqueous solutions, and the DCF:CD complexes did not show any FL signal (Fig. 2a). The second group contained only carboxymethyl- α -CD. Its aqueous solution did not exhibit any FL either. The EM spectrum of the DCF:CD solution showed the opposite trend, with a maximum at 380 nm (Fig. 2b). The third group contained the sodium salts of β -CD, the sulphated form of α -CD, and carboxymethyl- γ -CD. The EM spectra of DCF:CD in this group had slightly higher FL intensity than aqueous CDs (Fig. 2c). The fourth group consisted of (2-hydroxypropyl)- α -CD, hydroxypropyl- β -CD, and carboxymethyl- β -CD, which exhibited similar behaviour to that of solutions of CDs alone and their complexes with DCF. These complexes showed a shift in the location of the EM maximum and the FL intensity in the EM spectra was low (Fig. 2d).

The differences in the EM spectra of carboxymethyl- α -CD of the second group and its DCF complex were best suited for determining of DCF because the DCF:CD complex had a high FL intensity, while the aqueous solution of the CD alone did not emit any signal. The higher the DCF concentration, the higher the FL intensity of the DCF:CD complex. In contrast, the first group exhibited opposite behaviour. The signal of the DCF:CD complex decreased with increasing DCF concentrations. Using the third group would require extensive optimisation to maximize FL difference between minute DCF concentrations. The fourth group was not considered at all because the FL intensity was very low.

Our results did not reveal a general rule for the applicability of different types of CDs based on their cavity dimensions or functionalisation. Hydrates and some of the CDs modified with small functional groups appeared to fit in the first group. Salts appeared to fit in the third group. Some CDs with the larger functional groups fell in the fourth group.

We studied the stability of the DCF:CD complex with six CDs while not adjusted the pH of the reaction mixture, following the previously published studies that found the neutral range to be optimal for forming DCF:CD complexes [16,17,21]. For example, the results obtained for the DCF:carboxymethyl- α -CD complex are shown in Fig. S1. FL was measured every 5 min for 30 min. Only a slight decrease in the FL intensity was observed. Even after 2 h, the changes in FL intensity were within the experimental error of the measurements. For the sodium salts of sulphated α -CD and carboxymethyl- α -CD in the third group, an increase in FL intensity of 14.5 and 5.9 %, respectively, was observed in 30 min.

3.2. SIA measurements of FL properties of DCF:CD complexes

The on-line tests involved optimizing the aspirated volumes, the mixing method, and the stop-flow periods in order to obtain information on complex formation and stability. Initially, the volumes were set to 30 μL to achieve efficient mixing, and relatively short aspirated zones were mixed in the holding coil. If the mixing is not sufficient the flow reversal (s) can increase the zones' overlapping. The flow rate for the detection was optimised to obtain sufficient number of data points in the detector record. Thus, the flow rate and the detector scanning frequency both play an important role and must be properly selected. If a low number of points is applied for the flow measurement, data points at the peak maximum are missing, thus decreasing the repeatability and sensitivity of such measurement.

The main objective was to achieve a sensitive and selective determination of DCF, as concentrations below 10^{-5} mol/L were anticipated in the metabolic study. In this step, the sample volume was reduced to

Fig. 2. Emission spectra of 13 tested CDs and their CD:DCF complexes measured off-line; no FL signal for CD:DCF in part (a).

minimize sample consumption. Different concentrations of CD were also tested within the linear calibration range. Finally, we transferred the optimised conditions from the aqueous solutions to the solutions in the cultivation medium to maintain the conditions used in the metabolic study from which the real-life samples originated.

Five different SIA control programs were tested for mixing the aspirated zones within the flow system (Table S2). Program 1 used flow reversal to mix the DCF and CD zones that were aspirated into the holding coil. Then, the complex was transported into the detector. Program 2 compared mixing within the SIA system to off-line premixing solutions and simply aspirating the premixed zone, which was sent to the detector by flow reversal. Program 3 included efficient mixing with repeated flow reversal in the holding coil. The DCF and CD zones were aspirated, followed by the water zone. This mixture was then pushed to the detector after being mixed twice in the holding coil. Program 4 was based on a stop-flow step in the holding coil after the DCF and CD zones were aspirated. Finally, program 5 combined flow reversal mixing with a stop-flow step in the holding coil.

Experiments with α -CD hydrate mainly using programs 2 and 4 with stop-flow periods of 10–30 s, allowed comparison of DCF:CD at ratios of 1:1 and 1:2 (v/v). These experiments showed no difference between DCF and blank measurements. Similar results were obtained when carboxymethyl- α -CD was tested under the same conditions. Therefore, we returned to the first group of CDs and used (2-hydroxypropyl)- γ -CD despite expecting a decrease in FL intensity of the DCF:CD complex compared to the intensity of the aqueous CD. The results of the first experiments followed the expected trend. However, doubts arose about the preparation and storage of the solutions at laboratory and refrigerator temperatures, since the results obtained with fresh solutions were completely different.

Thus, we stored the prepared mixtures at room temperature for 24 h. The FL intensity of carboxymethyl- α -CD was significantly higher than that of the previously tested (2-hydroxypropyl)- γ -CD. This finding has also been observed previously [22] and explained by the formation of

aqueous hydrated DCF complexes in solution. These complexes changed the dimensions of the molecule, affecting its incorporation into the CD cavity. Based on our experiment, we stored all solutions at a laboratory temperature of 22 °C. We then tested an increase in FL intensity using control programs 4 and 5, which had stop-flow periods of 5, 10, and 20 min to extend the time for DCF:CD complex formation.

3.3. Effect of CD concentration on the SIA system with stop-flow in the holding coil

Extending the stop-flow time from 1 to 10 min did not provide any benefit. Therefore, a shorter stop-flow step was used for calibration to achieve on-line DCF determination faster. Reducing the CD concentration helped to achieve calibration linearity and repeatability at low DCF concentrations. For example, linearity was achieved with CD concentration of 1×10^{-2} mol/L for DCF concentrations above 5×10^{-6} mol/L. With 1×10^{-3} mol/L CD, the calibration range began at 1×10^{-6} mol/L DCF, yielding a coefficient of determination of 0.9306. Finally, with 1×10^{-4} mol/L CD, the calibration range was the same giving a coefficient of determination of 0.9934. The same conditions were tested for DCF solutions in cultivation medium, and similar trends were observed.

The repeatability ($n = 3$) of measurements with a 10 min stop-flow interval ranged from 1.66 to 10.57 %. With a 1 min stop-flow interval, the highest RSD values were 1.12, 1.53, and 0.78 % for CD at concentrations of 1×10^{-2} , 1×10^{-3} , and 1×10^{-4} mol/L, respectively. The RSD values increased to 2.22 % when the cultivation medium was used for DCF standard dilution. This value is still acceptable for rapid on-line SIA determinations.

3.4. Effect of DCF concentration on slope of calibration plot

The calibration range was tested under the conditions described in section 2.2., i.e., the volume and width of the scanned EX/EM bands, while the CD volume and concentration were 30 μ L and 1×10^{-4} mol/L,

respectively. In the same experiment, we investigated the effect of the excitation and emission bands width at 3 and 10 nm. The results revealed different relationships between fluorescence intensity and DCF concentration within the range of 5×10^{-7} and 1×10^{-6} mol/L. Here, a decrease in the measured signal was observed. For DCF concentrations higher than 5×10^{-6} and 1×10^{-5} mol/L, we observed the expected increase in fluorescence. This trend was also monitored for other concentrations of CD and for all control programs 3–5 shown in the Experimental section.

The parameter affecting the fluorescence properties of the DCF:CD complexes was found to be the ratio of the two components. At lower DCF concentrations, with two molecules of CD theoretically interacted with one molecule of DCF. At higher DCF concentrations, however, the ratio was 1:1 and the fluorescence intensity increased. The concentration range at which these properties changed from 5×10^{-7} to 1×10^{-6} mol/L (Fig. 3). It is possible that a single DCF molecule can be accommodated in two molecules of CD simultaneously, or that monomers and dimers of complexes formed in a ratio of 1:1 can be produced [23,24]. In our experiments, where a decrease in fluorescence intensity was observed at lower DCF concentrations, two mechanisms can be speculated: (i) a simple decrease in native CD fluorescence caused by interaction with DCF, and (ii) formation of a complex in excess of CD is formed by two molecules of CD and a single molecule of DCF. Similarly, we can speculate that (i) at higher DCF concentrations, the fluorescence intensity of the DCF:CD complex increases, or (ii) the 1:1 complex is more fluorescent than the 1:2 complex (Fig. 3).

Calibrations at higher concentrations were linear within the

1×10^{-6} – 5×10^{-6} mol/L range with coefficients of determination of 0.9920 and 0.9914, for 3 and 10 nm bands, respectively. The fluorescence intensities obtained using the 10 nm bands were approximately 60 times higher than those obtained using the 3 nm bands. Examples of the relation of FL intensity to DCF concentration are presented in the Supplementary material (Fig. S2–S3).

The limit of quantitation was investigated experimentally with respect to the difference in the two concentration intervals. Special attention was paid to the region where the relationship between FL intensity and DCF concentration changed. Therefore, the LOQ was set experimentally at 1×10^{-6} mol/L for the increasing part.

Complications arise when the expected DCF concentration level is unknown and the same FL intensities are found in both the decreasing and increasing regions. In this case, the applicability is limited just to identifying differences within the respective concentration ranges. This was the case in our study of real-life samples, where the added DCF amount was known, expected to decrease over time due to metabolism. However, this should also be considered and experimentally demonstrated for other types of samples or substances that form complexes with CDs.

To further increase the sensitivity, stop-flow was tested in the flow-through cuvette with a 240 μ L aspiration to stop the flow for 20 s after an increase in the fluorescence signal. The signal decreased for only a few data points (two or three) before increasing again. We evaluated the slope of this increase for the following 8 points (see the Supplementary material, Fig. S4 and S5). Unfortunately, the slopes for the 1×10^{-5} and 5×10^{-6} mol/L DCF standards were not sufficiently different

Fig. 3. Schematics of DCF:CD complexes formed at low (10^{-7} mol/L) and high (10^{-6} mol/L) concentrations ranges (a). (2-hydroxypropyl)- γ -CD (marked in yellow) has its own fluorescence that changes after complexing diclofenac (marked in orange). Comparison of relation of fluorescence intensities of complexes of diclofenac with (2-hydroxypropyl)- γ -CD (b). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

(17.44 and 17.36, respectively), so this approach could not be used to evaluate DCF concentration.

3.5. SIA determination of DCF in real-life samples

The determination of DCF in real-life samples from studies with primary human hepatocyte spheroids that were carried out in small volumes of tens of μL should be sensitive and selective enough to detect changes in low concentration that are not toxic to the tested cells. This corresponds to the small volume of samples available for determination, which is approximately 100–200 μL . Therefore, the volume of the DCF standards should also be reduced to 10 μL to minimize the volume for measurements in triplicate. A 10 μL of sample volume was required to wash the short sample tube and the sampling port. These parts were modified to minimize the volume and not to use more sample than necessary. With such modifications to the flow conditions, the sample-to-reagent ratio should remain the same, or the reagent should be used in higher excess to avoid re-optimisation. Although the volumes were decreased, the mixing efficiency remained unaffected. All other tests were performed with DCF standards prepared in cultivation medium.

The DCF standards were prepared in both glass and plastic vials to compare the effects of packing materials and freezing and thawing. The results obtained for samples stored in both types of vials were very similar. Freezing time did not affect the results of samples measured at room temperature after sufficient time had elapsed for melting to occur. The difference in the fluorescence intensity between identically prepared DCF standards in a cultivation medium, divided into glass and plastic vials and placed in the freezer for 24 h before melting, ranged from 0.12 % to 4.65 %. The average difference of 1.56 %, corresponded to the repeatability of the measurements.

Application to real-life samples began with the calibration close to the expected DCF concentration of about 1×10^{-5} mol/L. A (2-hydroxypropyl)- γ -CD concentration of 1×10^{-4} mol/L and an aspirated volume of 20 μL were used to achieve more effective mixing. Using five DCF concentration standards in the cultivation medium, the calibration range of $0.8\text{--}1.2 \times 10^{-5}$ mol/L was verified with excitation/emission bands of 3/3 and 5/3 nm with respective coefficients of determination of 0.9912 and 0.9997 (see Supplementary material, Fig. S6).

Real-life samples measurements were carried out with 5 samples in a cultivation medium containing a low amount of DMSO (0.3 % v/v), as well as 5 samples with the addition of 1×10^{-5} mol/L rifampicin in DMSO, which was used as a model substance to induce the metabolism in studies involving primary human hepatocyte spheroids. Two samples were always collected on days 1, 2, 3, 5, and 7 under the same conditions and for the same duration. The DCF content was previously determined

by LC-MS/MS [9]. First, we compared these results with those obtained by our method in the SIA system in a blind study that only compared the DCF concentration values. Later, we obtained the samples description and found that, in our experiments, the samples were measured in the following order: First, the sample from day 1 in the control and rifampicin variant, then a repetition of both, and then the samples from the other days using the same scheme (Fig. S7–S8). The initial LC-MS/MS results varied around 1×10^{-5} mol/L, showing an increasing trend during the first 3 days. This trend was probably caused by matrix effects when only simple dilution and filtration were applied to prepare the samples. The DCF concentration decreased in subsequent days. This decrease in DCF concentration was observed in the SIA determinations and better followed the expected hepatocyte activity. However, the complex composition of the real-life samples slightly increased the expected DCF concentration for EX/EM bands of 5/3 nm (Fig. S7) but corresponded well with bands of 3/3 nm (Fig. S8). These conditions were then applied to demonstrate the activity of primary human hepatocytes, as shown in Fig. 4. An excellent match was obtained between the DCF concentration values and those found by LC-MS/MS. The motivation to test two different EX/EM settings was based on higher FL values when broader EX band is applied. However, this also caused higher FL values in terms of comparison to LC-MS/MS. Thus, the proper EX/EM setting should be identified to achieve sufficient selectivity of FL determination in such a complex sample.

The interference of DMSO itself was tested and no problem was found. However, DMSO can enhance the fluorescence in an aqueous environment [25,26] and this should be kept in mind when DMSO is applied as a solvent even in very low concentration levels.

The repeatability of real-life samples measured by SIA in triplicate and expressed as RSD values was in the range of 0.14–4.61 %. Fig. 4 shows the trend of DCF metabolism, indicated by the enhanced fluorescence signal, where the samples are sorted by time of sampling and type of detection. The effect of rifampicin, which was tested for its ability to accelerate DCF metabolism, is evident in both the LC-MS/MS and the SIA-FL results. These results can help to predict the appropriate time to collect samples for off-line LC-MS/MS determination of the respective DCF metabolites.

The final step was straightforward because the on-line sampling from the apical and basolateral compartments of the 3D-printed module has already been demonstrated previously in toxicological applications studies [7,8]. Therefore, we applied the same concept from an analytical point of view. We tested the connection and on-line sampling at short time intervals, which can be extended according to the needs of metabolic studies. Future developments should focus on further miniaturization to work with primary human hepatocyte spheroids in well plates, where hepatocyte cells do not adhere and can behave as a real model of

Fig. 4. Diclofenac concentration changes in the 7 days long metabolic study comparing the results obtained using LC-MS/MS and SIA-FL methods; rifampicin (Rif) was tested to accelerate diclofenac metabolism; EX/EM bands 3/3 nm, sample volume 10 μL , 1×10^{-4} mol/L (2-hydroxypropyl)- γ -CD solution volume 20 μL .

metabolic pathways in the human body. An example of on-line monitoring at short intervals with double sampling at each sampling point is shown in the Supplementary material (Fig. S9).

3.6. Comparison of the developed DCF determination with previously published works

To compare the developed method with other possibilities for enhancing the sensitivity and selectivity of the analyte determination in a complex matrix, the previously published works are summarized in Table S3. The alternative is to preconcentrate the analyte using miniaturised extractions as a sample preparation technique, which allows for the manipulation of small sample volumes. Solid-phase extraction (SPE) techniques are the most commonly reported method for yielding pure extracts [27]. Low-sensitivity UV spectrophotometry coupled with HPLC separation or ion-associate formation has been sufficient for analysing DCF in simple matrices [28–30]. Increased sensitivity, which is required for analysing biological samples such as plasma, urine, and tissue, has been achieved using SPE, solid-phase microextraction and hollow-fibre solid/liquid phase microextraction [31,32]. Similar sensitivity has also been achieved using a molecularly imprinted polymer (MIP) as an SPE sorbent [27]. Further improvements have been achieved using hollow fibre carbon nanotubes and solid/liquid phase microextraction [33]. The limits of detection/quantitation using SPE preconcentration were 25-fold (SPE) lower or even 45-fold (MIP-SPE) lower compared to DCF:CD complexation. However, these extraction steps increased analysis time. According to green/white chemistry principles, sample preparation steps should be omitted if possible [34]. Thus, the developed method elegantly demonstrates how to eliminate tedious yet efficient sample preparation.

4. Conclusion

A rapid fluorometric on-line SIA method for determining DCF in samples from a metabolic study using primary human hepatocyte spheroids has been developed. The unique properties of DCF:CD complexes were investigated, optimised, and applied to sensitive and selective DCF determination in a complex matrix, consisting of a cultivation medium, DMSO or rifampicin, and DCF. The results obtained are comparable to off-line LC-MS/MS measurements. However, it should be noted that selectivity must be controlled by properly tuning the excitation/emission bandwidths and calibrating the matrix to include all the substances present in the samples. More accurate determinations can be achieved with LC-MS/MS and more specific sample pretreatment. Real-time SIA monitoring helps to visualize the metabolism in terms of concentration differences but does not necessarily provide the very accurate FL detection values, which can be affected by complex matrices. Our newly developed method allows for the fully automated monitoring of metabolic studies with a frequent sampling. Real-time results can then be used to predict the sampling intervals for off-line LC/MS metabolite determination according to the rate of DCF metabolism rate visualized by on-line SIA monitoring. These two methods can be efficiently combined to rapidly and accurately provide information on DCF metabolism. Additionally, the fluorescence properties of complexes with CDs can be optimised for other substances in metabolic studies, eliminating the need to analyse the native fluorescence of such analytes and focusing instead on their interaction with CDs.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ivana Pekařová: Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Michaela Váňová:** Visualization, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Petr Chocholouš:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **František Švec:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Conceptualization. **Hana Sklenářová:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Project

administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The author is an Editorial Board Member/Editor-in-Chief/Associate Editor/Guest Editor for this journal and was not involved in the editorial review or the decision to publish this article.

Acknowledgement

The authors appreciate the financial support of the project New Technologies for Translational Research in Pharmaceutical Sciences (NETPHARM, project ID CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004607), co-funded by the European Union.

The authors would like to express their special thanks to Dr. Tomáš Smutný, Ph.D. for samples from metabolic study and Dr. Lukáš Lochman, Ph.D. for sharing results of MS determination of diclofenac and these samples.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2025.128847>.

Data availability

I have shared data in Zenodo as DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14981526.

References

- [1] J. Ruzicka, G.D. Marshall, Sequential injection: a new concept for chemical sensors, process analysis and laboratory assays, *Anal. Chim. Acta* 237 (1990) 329–343, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0003-2670\(00\)83937-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0003-2670(00)83937-9).
- [2] E.A.G. Zagatto, A.C.F. Vida, P.J. Worsfold, Flow analysis – overview, in: P. Worsfold, C. Poole, A. Townshend, M. Miró (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of Analytical Science*, third ed., Elsevier Ltd., Amsterdam, 2016, pp. 213–219, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-409547-2.12202-4>.
- [3] C. Carderilla, F. Maya, L.O. Leal, V. Cerda, Recent advances in flow-based automated solid-phase extraction, *Trends Anal. Chem.* 108 (2018) 370–380, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2018.09.011>.
- [4] P.J. Worsfold, R. Clough, M.C. Lohan, P. Monbet, P.S. Ellis, C.R. Quétel, G.H. Floor, I.D. McKelvie, Flow injection analysis as a tool for enhancing oceanographic nutrient measurements—A review, *Anal. Chim. Acta* 803 (2013) 15–40, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2013.06.015>.
- [5] J. Ruzicka, Redesigning flow injection after 40 years of development: flow programming, *Talanta* 176 (2018) 437–443, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2017.08.061>.
- [6] J. Ruzicka, P. Chocholouš, Next generation of flow analysis is based on flow programming, *Talanta* 269 (2024) 125410, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2023.125410>.
- [7] L. Zelená, S.S. Marques, M.A. Segundo, M. Miró, P. Pávek, H. Sklenářová, P. Solich, Fully automatic flow-based device for monitoring of drug permeation across a cell monolayer, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 408 (2016) 971–981, <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s00216-015-9194-0>.
- [8] H. Sklenářová, M. Rosecká, B. Horstkotte, P. Pávek, M. Miró, P. Solich, 3D printed permeation module to monitor interaction of cell membrane transporters with exogenic compounds in real-time, *Anal. Chim. Acta* 1153 (2021) 338296, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2021.338296>.
- [9] L. Lochman, E.T. Kahiya, B. Saade, T. Smutný, J.D. Tebbens, P. Pávek, V. Bernhauerová, Quantifying expression and metabolic activity of genes regulated by pregnane X receptor in primary human hepatocyte spheroids, *PLoS Comput. Biol.* (2025), <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1012886>.
- [10] P. Mura, Analytical techniques for characterization of cyclodextrin complexes in aqueous solution: a review, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.* 101 (2014) 238–250, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpba.2014.02.022>.
- [11] M. Sayed, H. Pal, Supramolecularly assisted modulations in chromophoric properties and their possible applications: an overview, *J. Mater. Chem. C* 4 (2016) 2685–2706, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c5tc03321g>.
- [12] M. Kfoury, D. Landy, S. Fourmentin, Characterization of cyclodextrin/volatile inclusion complexes: a review, *Molecules* 23 (2018) 1204, <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules23051204>.

- [13] J. Zhang, H. Qiu, T. He, Y. Li, S. Yin, Fluorescent supramolecular polymers formed by crown ether-based host-guest interaction, *Front. Chem.* 8 (2020) 250, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fchem.2020.00560>.
- [14] T. Rasheed, F. Nabeel, K. Rizwan, M. Bilal, T. Hussain, S.A. Shehzad, Conjugated supramolecular architectures as state-of-the-art materials in detection and remedial measures of nitro based compounds: a review, *Trends Anal. Chem.* 129 (2020) 115958, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2020.115958>.
- [15] F. Yan, Y. Hou, C. Yi, Y. Wang, M. Xu, J. Xu, Carbon dots modified/prepared by supramolecular host molecules and their potential applications: a review, *Anal. Chim. Acta* 1232 (2022) 340475, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2022.340475>.
- [16] J.A. Arancibia, M.A. Boldrini, G.M. Escandar, Spectrofluorimetric determination of diclofenac in the presence of α -cyclodextrin, *Talanta* 52 (2000) 261–268, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0039-9140\(00\)00338-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0039-9140(00)00338-6).
- [17] A.A. Elbashir, N.F. Dsugi, T.O. Mohamed, H.Y. Aboul-Enein, Spectrofluorometric analytical applications of cyclodextrins, *Luminescence* 29 (2014) 1–7, <https://doi.org/10.1002/bio.2504>.
- [18] J.A. Arancibia, G.M. Escandar, Complexation study of diclofenac with beta-cyclodextrin and spectrofluorimetric determination, *Analyst* (1999) 1833–1838, <https://doi.org/10.1039/A906719A>.
- [19] S.K. Mehta, K.K. Bhasin, S. Dham, Energetically favorable interactions between diclofenac sodium and cyclodextrin molecules in aqueous media, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 326 (2) (2008) 374–381, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2008.06.039>.
- [20] A.M. Pimenta, A.N. Araújo, M.C.B.S.M. Montenegro, Simultaneous potentiometric and fluorimetric determination of diclofenac in a sequential injection analysis system, *Anal. Chim. Acta* 170 (2002) 185–194, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0003-2670\(02\)00669-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0003-2670(02)00669-4).
- [21] T.U. Sevgi, New and sensitive spectrofluorimetric method for the determination of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, etodolac and diclofenac sodium in pharmaceutical preparations through derivatization with 7-fluoro-4-nitrobenzo-2-oxa-1,3-diazole, *J. Food Drug Anal.* 19 (2011) 94–101, <https://doi.org/10.38212/2224-6614.2202>.
- [22] A.C.C. Rodrigues, L.O. Sallum, A.S.N. Aguiar, A.J. Camargo, H.C.B. Oliveira, H. B. Napolitano, Exploring the aqueous solubility and intermolecular interactions of diclofenac Diethylammonium: a molecular modeling study in solid state and solvation processes, *J. Mol. Liq.* 401 (2024) 124613, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2024.124613>.
- [23] A. Nakamura, S. Sato, K. Hamasaki, A. Ueno, F. Toda, Association of 1:1 inclusion complexes of cyclodextrins into homo- and heterodimers: a spectroscopic study using a TICT-forming fluorescent probe as a guest compound, *J. Phys. Chem.* 99 (1995) 10952–10959, <https://doi.org/10.1021/j100027a040>.
- [24] A. Roy, S. Saha, M.N. Roy, Study to explore host-guest inclusion complexes of cyclodextrins with biologically active molecules in aqueous environment, *Fluid Phase Equilib.* 425 (2016) 252–258, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fluid.2016.06.013>.
- [25] S.A. Markarian, G.A. Shahinyan, The effect of dimethylsulfoxide on absorption and fluorescence spectra of aqueous solutions of acridine orange base, *Spectrochim. Acta Mol. Biomol. Spectrosc.* 151 (2015) 662–666, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2015.06.126>.
- [26] S. Ravi, P. Priyadarshini, G. Deviga, M. Mariappan, S. Karthikeyan, M. Pannipara, A.G. Al-Sehemi, D. Moon, S.P. Anthony, Water sensitive fluorescence tuning of V-shaped ES IPT fluorophores: substituent effect and trace amount water sensing in DMSO, *Spectrochim. Acta Mol. Biomol. Spectrosc.* 309 (2024) 123838, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2024.123838>.
- [27] A.A. Pebdani, A.M. Shabani, S. Dadfarnia, S. Khodadoust, Solid phase microextraction of diclofenac using molecularly imprinted polymer sorbent in hollow fiber combined with fiber optic-linear array spectrophotometry, *Spectrochim. Acta Part A Mol Biomol Spectroscopy* 147 (2015) 26–30, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2015.03.057>.
- [28] Z.O. Kormosh, I.P. Hunka, Y.R. Bazel, A new analytical form for the spectrophotometric determination of low levels of diclofenac, *Methods and Objects, Chem. Anal.* 1 (2007) 76–81.
- [29] Z.O. Kormosh, I.P. Hunka, Y.R. Bazel, Extraction and spectrophotometric determination of diclofenac in pharmaceuticals, *J. Chin. Chem. Soc.* 55 (2008) 356–361, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jccs.200800052>.
- [30] B.X. Mayer, K. Namiranian, P. Dehghanyar, R. Stroh, H. Mascher, M. Müller, Comparison of UV and tandem mass spectrometric detection for the high-performance liquid chromatographic determination of diclofenac in microdialysis samples, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.* 33 (2003) 745–754, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0731-7085\(03\)00301-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0731-7085(03)00301-7).
- [31] A. Azzouz, B. Souhail, E. Ballesteros, Determination of residual pharmaceuticals in edible animal tissues by continuous solid-phase extraction and gas chromatography–mass spectrometry, *Talanta* 84 (2011) 820–828, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2011.02.016>.
- [32] L. Vera-Candioti, M.D. GilGarcía, M. Martínez Galera, H.C. Goicoechea, Chemometric assisted solid-phase microextraction for the determination of anti-inflammatory and antiepileptic drugs in river water by liquid chromatography–diode array detection, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1211 (2008) 22–32, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2008.09.093>.
- [33] X.Y. Song, Y.P. Shi, J. Chen, A novel extraction technique based on carbon nanotubes reinforced hollow fiber solid/liquid microextraction for the measurement of piroxicam and diclofenac combined with high performance liquid chromatography, *Talanta* 100 (2012) 153–161, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2012.08.042>.
- [34] P.T. Anastas, J.C. Warner, *Green Chemistry – Theory and Practice*, Oxford University Press, New York, USA, 2000. ISBN: 9780198506980.